

1 Python Code

This file contains the implementation we deem necessary for the completion of our paper.

1.1 Entanglement for 2-qubit

We use the following computational basis for the two-qubit case.

$$|00\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad |01\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad |10\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad |11\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

In the case of two qubits, the amount of entanglement of the state $|\psi\rangle$ is given by the following expression.

$$\Delta(|\psi\rangle) = 2 |c_{00}c_{11} - c_{01}c_{10}| \quad (2)$$

```
import numpy as np

# Programming for calculating entanglement in the 2-qubit case

def to_complex_normalized(v):
    n = int ( len(list(v)) / 2)
    v = np.array([v[i] + 1j*v[n + i] for i in range(n)])
    v = v / np.sqrt(np.vdot(v,v))
    return v

def entanglment_2_qubit(v):
    ent = 2 * abs(v[0]*v[3] - v[1]*v[2])
    return np.round(ent,6)

w_example = np.array([1,1,-1,1,-1,1,1,1])
v1 = to_complex_normalized(w_example)
print("Entanglement=", entanglment_2_qubit(v1))
```

1.2 Entanglement (Concurrence) for 3-qubit

In the following, we provide a program that analyzes the 3-qubit case using concurrence, examining the 1-to-1, 1-to-2, and overall entanglement. The computational basis is assumed to

be defined as shown below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 |000\rangle &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, & |001\rangle &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, & |010\rangle &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, & |011\rangle &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \\
 |100\rangle &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, & |101\rangle &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, & |110\rangle &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, & |111\rangle &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix},
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

```

import numpy as np
from scipy.linalg import sqrtm, eigh

# Transformation using the map phi: R^16 -> C^8
def to_complex_normalized(v):
    v = np.array([v[i] + 1j*v[8 + i] for i in range(8)])
    v = v / np.sqrt(np.vdot(v,v))
    return v

# 3-qubit conversion:
# Converts a vector in C^8 into a rank-3 tensor of shape (2, 2, 2)
def tensor_trans_np(v):
    v = np.asarray(v, dtype=np.complex128)
    return np.array([
        [[v[0], v[1]], [v[2], v[3]]],
        [[v[4], v[5]], [v[6], v[7]]]
    ])

# Define the partial trace Tr_A(rho)
def P_Trace_A_np(v):
    T = tensor_trans_np(v)
    rho = np.zeros((4, 4), dtype=np.complex128)
    num_list = [(0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1)]
    for i, A in enumerate(num_list):
        for j, B in enumerate(num_list):
            s = sum(T[k][A[0]][A[1]] * np.conj(T[k][B[0]][B[1]]) for k in range(2))
            rho[i, j] = s
    return rho

# Define the partial trace Tr_B(rho)
def P_Trace_B_np(v):
    T = tensor_trans_np(v)
    rho = np.zeros((4, 4), dtype=np.complex128)
    num_list = [(0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1)]
    for i, A in enumerate(num_list):
        for j, B in enumerate(num_list):
            s = sum(T[A[0]][k][A[1]] * np.conj(T[B[0]][k][B[1]]) for k in range(2))
            rho[i, j] = s
    return rho

```

```

# Define the partial trace Tr_C(rho)
def P_Trace_C_np(v):
    T = tensor_trans_np(v)
    rho = np.zeros((4, 4), dtype=np.complex128)
    num_list = [(0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1)]
    for i, A in enumerate(num_list):
        for j, B in enumerate(num_list):
            s = sum(T[A[0]][A[1]][k] * np.conj(T[B[0]][B[1]][k]) for k in range(2))
            rho[i, j] = s
    return rho

# Pairwise (two-qubit) entanglement measures
def C_BC_concurrence(v):
    rho = P_Trace_A_np(v)
    rho_sqrt = sqrtm(rho)

    sigma_y = np.array([[0, -1j], [1j, 0]])
    sigma_y_2 = np.kron(sigma_y, sigma_y)

    rho_final = rho_sqrt @ sigma_y_2 @ np.conj(rho) @ sigma_y_2 @ rho_sqrt

    eigvals = eigh(rho_final, eigvals_only=True)
    eigvals_sorted = np.sort(np.sqrt(np.maximum(eigvals, 0)))[:-1]
    return float(np.real(eigvals_sorted[0] - eigvals_sorted[1] - eigvals_sorted[2] - eigvals_sorted[3]))

def C_CA_concurrence(v):
    rho = P_Trace_B_np(v)
    rho_sqrt = sqrtm(rho)

    sigma_y = np.array([[0, -1j], [1j, 0]])
    sigma_y_2 = np.kron(sigma_y, sigma_y)

    rho_final = rho_sqrt @ sigma_y_2 @ np.conj(rho) @ sigma_y_2 @ rho_sqrt

    eigvals = eigh(rho_final, eigvals_only=True)
    eigvals_sorted = np.sort(np.sqrt(np.maximum(eigvals, 0)))[:-1]
    return float(np.real(eigvals_sorted[0] - eigvals_sorted[1] - eigvals_sorted[2] - eigvals_sorted[3]))

def C_AB_concurrence(v):
    rho = P_Trace_C_np(v)
    rho_sqrt = sqrtm(rho)

    sigma_y = np.array([[0, -1j], [1j, 0]])
    sigma_y_2 = np.kron(sigma_y, sigma_y)

    rho_final = rho_sqrt @ sigma_y_2 @ np.conj(rho) @ sigma_y_2 @ rho_sqrt

    eigvals = eigh(rho_final, eigvals_only=True)
    eigvals_sorted = np.sort(np.sqrt(np.maximum(eigvals, 0)))[:-1]
    return float(np.real(eigvals_sorted[0] - eigvals_sorted[1] - eigvals_sorted[2] - eigvals_sorted[3]))

# One-versus-two entanglement measures
def C_A_BC_concurrence(v):
    return abs(np.sqrt(2 * (1 - (P_Trace_A_np(v) @ P_Trace_A_np(v)).trace()) ))

def C_B_CA_concurrence(v):
    return abs(np.sqrt(2 * (1 - (P_Trace_B_np(v) @ P_Trace_B_np(v)).trace()) ))

def C_C_AB_concurrence(v):
    return abs(np.sqrt(2 * (1 - (P_Trace_C_np(v) @ P_Trace_C_np(v)).trace()) ))

# Overall (global) entanglement measure
def Q_concurrence(v):
    return 1/2 * (C_A_BC_concurrence(v) + C_B_CA_concurrence(v) + C_C_AB_concurrence(v))

# F3: a function of Q and pairwise entanglements

```

```

def F3_concurrence(v):
    conA = C_A_BC_concurrence(v)
    conB = C_B_CA_concurrence(v)
    conC = C_C_AB_concurrence(v)
    Q_con = Q_concurrence(v)
    return 4 / np.sqrt(3) * np.sqrt(Q_con * (Q_con - conA) * (Q_con - conB) * (Q_con - conC))

# Example usage
w_example = [1, -1, 3, 1, -1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1]
v_complex = to_complex_normalized(w_example)
print("C_{AB}=", np.abs(np.round(C_AB_concurrence(v_complex), 6)))
print("C_{CA}=", np.abs(np.round(C_CA_concurrence(v_complex), 6)))
print("C_{BC}=", np.abs(np.round(C_BC_concurrence(v_complex), 6)))
print("C_{A(BC)}=", np.round(C_A_BC_concurrence(v_complex), 6))
print("C_{B(CA)}=", np.round(C_B_CA_concurrence(v_complex), 6))
print("C_{C(AB)}=", np.round(C_C_AB_concurrence(v_complex), 6))
print("Q = ", np.round(Q_concurrence(v_complex), 6))
print("F3 = ", np.round(F3_concurrence(v_complex), 6))

```

then you will be obtaining as

```

C_{AB}= 0.0
C_{CA}= 0.0
C_{BC}= 0.0
C_{A(BC)}= 0.816497
C_{B(CA)}= 0.816497
C_{C(AB)}= 0.816497
Q = 1.224745
F3 = 0.666667

```

1.3 Magic

In the case of a general n -qudit system, Ξ_α is defined as

$$\Xi_\alpha(|\psi\rangle) \equiv \frac{1}{d^n} \sum_{\mathcal{O} \in \mathcal{W}(n,d)} |\langle \psi | \mathcal{O} | \psi \rangle|^{2\alpha}, \quad (4)$$

and the magic is defined by

$$M_\alpha(|\psi\rangle) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log \Xi_\alpha(|\psi\rangle). \quad (5)$$

In the following, we present a program that computes this quantity. Unless otherwise stated, we use $\alpha = 2$ throughout.

1.4 Magic for 2-qubit

We will use the basis defined in 1. The code for computing the magic is given below.

```

import numpy as np
from itertools import product

# Program for calculating magic in the 2-qubit case

# Transform a vector from R^8 to C^4 and normalize it

def to_complex_normalized(v):
    n = int ( len(list(v)) / 2)
    v = np.array([v[i] + 1j*v[n + i] for i in range(n)])
    v = v / np.sqrt(np.vdot(v,v))
    return v

# Pauli matrices (complex dtype)

```

```

0 = np.array([[1, 0], [0, 1]], dtype=complex)
1 = np.array([[0, 1], [1, 0]], dtype=complex)
2 = np.array([[0, -1j], [1j, 0]], dtype=complex)
3 = np.array([[1, 0], [0, -1]], dtype=complex)
pauli = [0, 1, 2, 3]

# -----
# Definition of magic for 2-qubit
# Maximum magic:  $\log_2(16/7) \sim 1.192645$ 
# Magic of stabilizer states: 0
# -----

def magic_2qubit_numpy(psi):
    psi = np.asarray(psi, dtype=complex).reshape(-1, 1)
    psi = psi / np.sqrt(np.vdot(psi, psi)) # normalize
    rho = psi @ psi.conj().T # outer product  $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ 

    Xi_2 = 0
    for i, j in product(range(4), repeat=2):
        P = np.kron(pauli[i], pauli[j])
        tr = np.trace(rho @ P)
        Xi_2 += abs(tr)**4 / 4
    return float(np.log2(1 / Xi_2))

```

1.4.1 Magic for 3-qubits

We use the basis defined in 3.

```

import numpy as np
from itertools import product

# Program for calculating magic in the 3-qubit case

# Transform a vector from  $\mathbb{R}^{16}$  to  $\mathbb{C}^8$  and normalize it

def to_complex_normalized(v):
    n = int ( len(list(v)) / 2)
    v = np.array([v[i] + 1j*v[n + i] for i in range(n)])
    v = v / np.sqrt(np.vdot(v,v))
    return v

# Pauli matrices (complex dtype)
sigma0 = np.array([[1, 0], [0, 1]], dtype=complex)
sigma1 = np.array([[0, 1], [1, 0]], dtype=complex)
sigma2 = np.array([[0, -1j], [1j, 0]], dtype=complex)
sigma3 = np.array([[1, 0], [0, -1]], dtype=complex)
pauli = [sigma0, sigma1, sigma2, sigma3]

# define the magic for 3-qubit
def magic_3qubit_numpy(psi):
    psi = np.asarray(psi, dtype=complex).reshape(-1, 1)
    psi = psi / np.sqrt(np.vdot(psi, psi)) # normalize
    rho = psi @ psi.conj().T # outer product  $|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ 

    Xi_2 = 0
    for i, j, k in product(range(4), repeat=3):
        P = np.kron(np.kron(pauli[i], pauli[j]), pauli[k])
        tr = np.trace(rho @ P)
        Xi_2 += abs(tr)**4 / 8 #  $2^3 = 8$ 
    return float(np.log2(1 / Xi_2))

w_example = [1, -1, 3, 1, -1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1]
v_complex = to_complex_normalized(w_example)
print(magic_3qubit_numpy(v_complex))

```

This yields the following result:

1.4.2 The magic for 1-qutrit

The Weyl–Heisenberg group, which generalizes the Pauli matrices, is defined in the main paper. In terms of explicit operators, it can be expressed as

$$X = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} |i+1\rangle \langle i|, \quad Z = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} \omega^i |i\rangle \langle i|, \quad \text{where } \omega = e^{2\pi i/d}. \quad (6)$$

Now, setting $d = 3$, their matrix representations are given as follows.

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad Z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \omega & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \omega^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where

$$|0\rangle \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad |1\rangle \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad |2\rangle \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

the phase-quotiented Weyl–Heisenberg group is given by

$$\mathcal{W}(1,3) = \{D_{a_1, a_2} \mid a_1, a_2 \in \{0, 1, 2\}\},$$

and consists of 9 elements in total, where $D_{\mathbf{a}} \equiv \tau^{a_1 a_2} X^{a_1} Z^{a_2}$ and $\tau = \omega^2$. The following code is the one for calculating the magic of 1-qutrit.

```
import numpy as np

# Definition of omega, D(a,b), and WH group
omega = np.exp(2j * np.pi / 3)
X = np.array([[0, 1, 0], [0, 0, 1], [1, 0, 0]], dtype=complex)
Z = np.array([[1, 0, 0], [0, omega, 0], [0, 0, np.conj(omega)]], dtype=complex)

def D(a, b):
    return np.conj(omega)**(a * b) * np.linalg.matrix_power(X, a) @ np.linalg.matrix_power(Z, b)

WH_group = [D(a, b) for a in range(3) for b in range(3)]

# -----
# Definition of magic for a single qutrit
# Maximum magic: 1
# Magic of stabilizer states: 0
# -----

def magic_value_1_qutrit(v):
    v = np.array(v)
    v = v / np.linalg.norm(v)
    rho = np.outer(v, np.conj(v))
    summ = 0
    for D in WH_group:
        summ += abs(np.trace(D @ rho))**4 / 3
    return np.round(np.abs(-np.log2(summ.real)), 8)
```

2 MAGMA

In this section, we briefly introduce a tool for investigating properties of lattices. The website known as the *Magma Computational Algebra System* (Magma Online Calculator) is developed and maintained by the *Computational Algebra Group* at the University of Sydney, Australia. It is widely known to be highly useful for exploring properties of lattices and related algebraic structures.

Here is a basic example of how to use it. Suppose we want to determine properties such as the kissing number and the automorphism group of a lattice (e.g., the D_4 lattice) generated as follows:

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

then the code you should put is as follows

```
M := Matrix(4, 4, [1, -1, 0, 0, 0, 1, -1, 0, 0, 0, 1, -1, 0, 0, 1, 1]);
L := LatticeWithBasis(M);
Aut := AutomorphismGroup(L : NaturalAction);
KissingNumber(L);
L, Aut;
```

After entering the above code, the result you will obtain is as follows.

```
24
Lattice of rank 4 and degree 4
Determinant: 4
Factored Determinant: 2^2
Minimum: 2
Kissing Number: 24
Basis:
( 1 -1 0 0)
( 0 1 -1 0)
( 0 0 1 -1)
( 0 0 1 1)

MatrixGroup(4, Rational Field) of order 2^7 * 3^2
Generators:
[ 0 0 1 0]
[ 1 0 0 0]
[ 0 -1 0 0]
[ 0 0 0 1]

[ 1/2 1/2 1/2 1/2]
[-1/2 1/2 1/2 -1/2]
[-1/2 -1/2 1/2 1/2]
[-1/2 1/2 -1/2 1/2]

[ 1 0 0 0]
[ 0 1 0 0]
[ 0 0 0 -1]
[ 0 0 -1 0]
```

Magma Online Calculator is used not only for information about lattices but also for calculating properties such as the order of finite groups. For example, in the case of the 1-quitrit Clifford group, its order can be computed using the following command.

```
// Clifford Group for 1-quitrit.
Q<w> := CyclotomicField(3); // Define the field extension Q[omega]
```

```

K<r> := ext<Q | Polynomial([-3, 0, 1])>; // The field K include sqrt3 over Q[omega]

R := MatrixAlgebra(K, 3);
omega := K!w; // omega -> K
sqrt3inv := 1 / r; // r = sqrt3

// Define the H and S
H := sqrt3inv * R![1,1,1, 1,omega,omega^2, 1,omega^2,omega];
S := R![1,0,0, 0,1,0, 0,0,omega];

// Generate the group and show its order
G := sub< GL(3, K) | H, S >;
#G;

```